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Authoritative Works on Rāja Yoga - A Brief Reflective

Sunitha S.¹

Abstract

Patañjali's Yogasūtra stands out to be the most formidable treatise on yoga philosophy and practice. The Aṣṭāṅgās, the eight-fold limbs/paths as ascribed in Yogasūtra, forms the basic tenets of all the different tributaries and ramification of Yoga traditions developed as of today. Essentially the most important writings on Rāja yoga are those on the Yogasūtra and the Aṣṭāṅgās in it. These works come under two chronological categories, the first by authors during the middle of the first millennium CE, consisting of 'Bhāṣyas' (commentaries) and 'Vivaraṇas' (sub-commentaries) on Yogasūtra. These are mostly in Sanskrit. Vyāsabhāṣya is quite elaborative in its word by word analysis of Yoga sūtra. The second category of Yogasūtra commentary works predominantly emerges from the later part of the 2nd millennium CE. Swami Vivekananda's 'Rāja yoga' is generally ascribed as the flagship of such a fleet of subsequent works. The most profound among the recent works on Patañjali's Yogasūtra has been B.K.S. Iyengar's 'Light on Yogasūtras of Patañjali'.

Key Words

Patañjali, Yogasūtra, Aṣṭāṅgās, Rāja yoga, Bhāṣyās, Vivaraṇās

Introduction

The eternal quest of men, the enquiry towards existential essence and immortality is an innate quality. The question is whether it is limited to his/her earthly fame and name or extended beyond to life after life. Every culture has its own answers and solutions for actualization that have eventually been systematised to verbal and textual codes. These are mainly compositions of the teachings of a single Master (prophet)

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or many Masters (gurus). The former includes organised religions such as Christianity, Islam and Buddhism while the latter category is mostly ascribed to Hinduism. Hinduism in its entirety is an amalgamation of varied thoughts, ideas and principles on life, living and beyond, emanated from contemplative minds from antiquity that assumed many a theistic, atheistic and agnostic trails in different terrains of the posterity. The adventures of human consciousness could be found its most profound outcomes in Śad Darśanās.

Works on Rāja yoga

Hinduism, also called Sanāthana Dharma. Yoga darśana is prime among darśanas, others being Nyāya, Sāmkhya, Vaiśeṣika, Pūrvamīmāmsa and Uttaramīmāmsa or Vedānta (Radhakrishnan 2008). The most original and authentic textual treatise of Yoga darśana is Mahārṣi Patañjali's Yogasūtra (Dasgupta 2018: p. 229; Vivekananda 2016; Iyengar 2002: pp.1-2). Yogasūtra is more on practices (Sādhanās) and their resultant physical and spiritual attainments, rather than on mere theoretical postulates and esoteric debates. The bhāṣyakārās (commentators) and scholars from Vyāsa to B.K.S. Iyengar considers Patañjali as the first and foremost figure to synthesise and organise knowledge about yoga, concourse all through antiquity, into a compilation containing 196 sūtrās (aphorisms). The time of compilation of Yogasūtra by Patañjali, as a consensus, is assumed to be sometime in the early centuries CE (Iyengar 2002: p.1; Leggett 1992: p.4). Scholars on darśanas (Indian philosophy) have generally attributed three traditions to have contributed to Yoga darśana, namely, the Sāmkhya (among the Śad darśanas), Abhidharma (of Buddhism) and ancient ascetic tradition. Yoga conforms to the ascetic tradition with regard to the concept of a supreme primaevial power in the helm of the entire universal affairs, while the former two traditions are either aesthesis or agnostic in this regard. In most of the other philosophical ideas the three traditions share identical stands (Leggett 1992: pp.3-4; Maehle 2016: pp.1-5).

Patañjali being considered the forefather of Yoga darśana, his magnum opus, Yogasūtra stands out to be the most formidable treatise on yoga philosophy and practice. The Aṣṭāṅgās, the eight-fold limbs/

paths as ascribed in Yogasūtra, almost exclusively forms the basic tenets of all the different tributaries and ramification of Yoga traditions developed as of today. Eventually, the Aṣṭāṅgās tradition of Patañjali being considered the epitome of the Yoga edifice, it is also called the Rāja yoga tradition, the royal among all paths. This is also the most assured route to realisation, proposed by Lord Krishna to warrior Arjuna, as described in the 4th chapter of Bhagavatgīta (Yogananda 2002: pp. 421-528). Essentially the most important writings on Rāja yoga are those on the Yogasūtra and the Aṣṭāṅgās in it. These works come under two chronological categories, the first by authors during the middle of the first millennium CE, consisting of 'Bhāṣyas' (commentaries) and 'Vivaraṇās' (sub-commentaries) on Yogasūtra. These are mostly in Sanskrit. The second category of Yogasūtra commentary works predominantly emerges from the later part of the 2nd millennium CE onwards. Swami Vivekananda's 'Rāja yoga' is generally ascribed as the flagship of such a fleet of subsequent works.

Sūtras as a rule, as also Yogasūtra, are condensed verses called aphorisms consisting of only the crux of the matter to be conveyed. These require elaboration by learnt exponents, and such scholarly and critical narrations are called Bhāṣyas. The foremost, commentary on Patañjali's Yogasūtra is 'Yoga Bhāṣya' by Vyāsa, mostly consented as the same author of the epic 'Mahābhārata' and the 'Bhāgavata Purāṇa' and who codified and classified the Chatur Vedās (Baba 1976). He is considered to have lived some time between CE 540 and CE 650. The next accomplished commentary belongs to Vacaspati Misra, dated about 850 CE. Vacaspati's critical commentary encompasses both Patañjali's Yogasūtra and its Vyāsa Bhāṣya. These three works, namely Patañjali's Yogasūtra (about BCE 300), Vyāsa Bhāṣya (about 600 CE) and Vacaspati's Vivaraṇa (sub-commentary) laid the foundation for the Rāja yoga school of Yoga philosophy (Leggett 1992: p.4).

Patañjali's Yogasūtra consists of 196 (or 195 as differently considered by many) sūtras or aphorisms, that are divided into four 'pādas' or chapters (Iyengar 2002: p.3). The backbone of Yoga sūtra is Aṣṭāṅgās (eight limbs/steps), prescribing the practical steps and stages to start with Yama (moral principles and behavioural ethics to excel in interpersonal relations), and Niyama (individual

physical and mental observances to be followed for intrapersonal development), Āsana (the suitable physical posture to be stabilised for further yoga practices), Prāṇāyāma (breathing practices to gain control of life force or prāṇa), Pratyāhāra (bringing the outward oriented ‘pañcha indriyas’ or the five senses towards the inner focus), Dhāraṇa (maintaining the inner focus of the mind in a state of ease), Dhyāna (on attaining control on senses, to anchor in mental peace and tranquillity in as much time as desired) and finally Samādhi (attainment of the state of pure consciousness – a stage of egoless, expanded awareness and sustained experience of bliss; a consequence of full command over will and cessation of thoughts and emotions arising in the mind).

The first chapter, Samādhipāda, deals with the objective and goal of Yoga i.e., Samādhi. The second chapter, Sādhanapāda, puts forth the practical part of yoga up to pratyāhāra, the 5th of the Aṣṭāṅgās. The third chapter, Vibhūtipāda, deals with the last three of the Aṣṭāṅgās i.e. the Antaraṅga Sādhanās of Dhāraṇa, Dhyāna and Samādhi, and a large part on the astral-mystical powers or ‘vibhūtis’ likely to be got hold of by the Yoga sādhanika in the advanced stages of Yoga sādhanā. The fourth chapter, Kaivalyapāda, considered by many scholars as a later addition, is on the ultimate liberation of the individual self into its pure consciousness and equating and becoming One with the Super Self; the ‘Kevala’ stage of the ‘One and the Only’. This reverberates with the Monistic philosophy of Vedānta darśana and as such the interpolation theory attributed with the Kaivalyapāda holds substance.

Vyāsabhāṣya is quite elaborative in its word-by-word analysis of Yoga sūtra; every word is explained in terms of etymology, meaning allusions and contexts. It is undisputable that Vyāsa has expounded the Bhāṣya while remaining in a state of dhyāna and extended state of awareness. In that super conscious state of creativity, he must have been in a plane of mental identity and ideational communion with the Yoga sūtra author, Maharṣi Patañjali. The identity is so much evident in the Bhāṣya that some scholars even doubt whether Vyāsa and Patañjali were the same. For the first aphorism of Yogasūtra i.e. “Adha Yogānuśāsanam”, Vyāsa confirms in the commentary that “Yogam Samādhiṃ” – Yoga is nothing but Samādhi; the mental

equanimity that has to be attained through aṣṭāṅgā sādhana. Samādhi is experienced in its super mental virtues of Ānanda (bliss), Ekāgra (concentration) and Niruddha (restraint) (Baba 1976: pp.1-2).

The Vivaraṇa (sub commentary) of Vacaspati Misra conforms to the classical yoga school that is more affiliated to the Sankara Vedānta: the omniscient God projects, maintains and withdraws the universe by His divine power called Māya. Everything, which is created, is unreal or transient and there is only one reality i.e., the Brahman, what may be equated to Patañjali's Īśwara (Leggett 1992: p.4).

It is generally avowed that the modern genre of commentaries on Yoga sūtra largely commences with the acclaimed work, 'Rāja yoga', by Swami Vivekananda. Vivekananda's transliteration, translation and commentary on Yoga sūtra, the original work in Sanskrit, stands out due to its lucidity and steadfastness, and particularly owing to the care taken to avoid undue philosophical debates and intellectual extravagance. Vivekananda's commentary on Patañjali's Yoga aphorisms, being the creative product of a super conscious and spiritually assertive mind, withstands any tests of time and scholastic inquisition. In his introductory words on Yoga aphorisms, Vivekananda in his usual assertive style puts down the generally held modern theory that "man's destiny is to go on always improving, always struggling towards, and never reaching the goal" (Vivekananda 2003: pp. 80-85). He avers that there are much higher states of existence beyond the capability of the phenomenal level of mental reasoning. He postulates that, such as every form in this world has taken out of corresponding atoms and goes back to those atoms, we all came from God, and we are all bound to go back to God. The Yoga school of philosophy is emphatic that going back to God is the highest state and Rāja yoga shows the way and provides the scientific means that is unailing, if followed systematically.

The most profound among the recent works on Patañjali's Yogasūtra has been B.K.S. Iyengar's 'Light on Yogasūtras of Patañjali'. Iyengar being a doyen on Yoga and the protagonist yogāsana performer and propagandist, especially in the West, is a most rightful person to undertake the heavy task of translating and supplementing Yoga sūtra

with an elaborate commentary. Godfrey Devereux, the renowned western Yoga scholar and author of 'Dynamic Yoga', in his foreword for Iyengar's work has observed that "B.K.S. Iyengar's translation, based on over fifty years of dedicated and accomplished practice and teaching, is unique in its relevance and utility to contemporary yoga practitioners. It offers a lucid and pragmatic interpretation of the insights and subtleties of Yoga's root guru" (Iyengar 2002: p.viii).

The uniqueness of Iyengar's interpretation is that he provides all probable synonyms for every word of the aphorisms, so that even the learner not in acquaintance with Sanskrit could attempt his/her personal choice in explicating their meaning and allusions. In his introductory note Iyengar, while justifying his own effort of writing Yogasūtra commentary, puts that "as with the Bhagavad Gīta, different schools of thought have interpreted the sūtras in various ways, placing the emphasis on their particular path towards Self-realization. The commentator bases his interpretations on certain key or focal themes and weaves around them his thoughts, feelings and experiences" (Iyengar 2002: p.3). He also avers that his interpretations of Yoga sūtras were derived from his practice of āsana, Prāṇāyāma and dhyāna. He didn't make any claim that he had attained the final goal i.e., Samādhi or his interpretations assume that depth and infallibility accordingly. Of course, this aspect stands out as the limiting factor of Iyengar's interpretation of Yoga sūtra. In conformity with his own statement, it can be found that Iyengar interpreted Yoga sūtra in the simplest and most direct way, without departing from traditional meanings given by successive teachers. It can also be ascertained that any sādḥaka pursuing the aṣṭāṅgā path of Rāja yoga will find B.K.S. Iyengar's 'Light on Yoga Sūtrās of Patañjali' a path finding companion.

Conclusion

A brief overview of authentic texts based on Rāja yoga has been attempted. Innumerable Indian and foreign, especially western, scholars, Yoga enthusiasts and spiritual seekers adhering formidably to the Rāja yoga tradition of Saint Patañjali, have attempted and authored interpretations on Yoga sūtra and Aṣṭāṅgā Yoga. To mention

a few among them having wide reading and publicity includes ‘Yoga Sūtra of Patañjali with Commentary of Vyāsa’ by Bangali Baba (Baba 1976), ‘The Heart of Yoga’ by T.K.V. Desikachar (Desikachar 1995), ‘History of Indian Philosophy’ by Surendranath Dasgupta (Dasgupta 2018), ‘Rāja yoga’ by Swami Sivananda (Sivananda 2009), ‘Rāja yoga’ by Wallace Slater (Slater 2006), ‘Aṣṭāṅgā Yoga’ by Gregor Maehle (Maehle 2016) etc. The literary spectrum on Rāja yoga and Aṣṭāṅgā yoga is abound with a wide range of research article publications as well, exploring the different practical dimensions viz., health and longevity, therapeutic applications, mental and intellectual frames, aesthetic and esoteric dimensions and all the more, fathoms of consciousness (Mc. Kenzie 1922; Pandey 2011; Moorthy 1997).

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